

DEVELOPMENT OF POSITIVE INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS OF STUDENTS BY MEANS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING

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Abstract. The article considers the problem of developing positive interpersonal relationships of students in the process of psychological training. A brief overview of modern domestic scientific research on interpersonal relationships in children's, school and student groups is given. The results of a diagnostic study of interpersonal relationships of students of a medical university are presented. Based on the data obtained, the authors developed and implemented a psychological training "Psychology of Communication and Interpersonal Relationships"; its importance for the training of future teachers is substantiated. Analysis of the results of the control stage of the study showed that psychological training contributes to the development of effective interpersonal relationships, strengthening interpersonal ties, forming constructive interactions, and also promotes team building.

Keywords: development, student, psychological training, analysis.

Modern Uzbek society requires specialists who are able to competently, actively and creatively approach the solution of complex professional problems. In this regard, one of the urgent and significant problems of training teaching staff is the problem of developing students' communicative competence, the ability to effectively interact and understand each other in a team. Interpersonal relationships are one of the important factors in the emotional climate of a group and the emotional well-being of its members. The sphere of higher education has significant potential for the development of a personality capable of building effective interpersonal relationships that create the basis for successful professional self-realization. Student age is the period of the beginning of independent adult life. For a student, group interpersonal interaction and communication in a company of peers are most relevant. Interpersonal communication is not intentionally established by anyone; in most cases, it is not organizationally formalized, especially in the initial period of university education. The results of the study show that in the first year, not all student groups have a clearly expressed status of a close-knit team. Some of them are characterized by interpersonal isolation, detachment of individual group members. Therefore, it is important to develop positive interpersonal interaction skills in students.

For many years, the problem under consideration has been relevant and is widely represented in the works of a number of scientists. Recent studies have reflected the features of interpersonal relationships in children's (E.B. Shalonko, S.V. Kahnovich, E.I. Stryuk, etc.), school (T.A. Bugrenkova, N.A. Shkurecheva, etc.) and student groups (T.S. Sergeychik, A.K. Kanamatova, etc.).

In psychological dictionaries, the concept of "interpersonal relationships" is interpreted as "subjectively experienced relationships between people, objectively manifested in the nature and methods of mutual influence exerted by people on each other in the process of joint activities and communication" [4].

Kondratieva notes the special importance of psychological training in the development of communication skills of pupils and students, due to the fact that with their help it is possible to form skills of establishing contacts, constructive behavior, effective interaction with others and a positive attitude towards them [1].

Within the framework of the designated problem, a study was conducted at the Samarkand State Medical University. The total sample size was 38 first-year students of the pediatric faculty. The diagnostic program of the experimental study included the following methods:

"diagnostics of interpersonal relations" (T. Leary);

"methodology for assessing the psychological atmosphere in the team (according to A.F. Fidler)";

"questionnaire of interpersonal relations (IPR)" (A.A. Rukavishnikov);

"determination of the Seashore group cohesion index".

To identify the types of interpersonal relations of students, the method "Diagnostics of interpersonal relations" (T. Leary) was carried out. The data analysis showed that 18.8% of respondents have an authoritarian type of attitude towards people around them. Students of this type are leaders in all types of activities, they have a dominant and dictatorial character, they strive to instruct, teach people around them and demand respect. 20.8% of respondents have a dominant egoistic type of interpersonal relations, which indicates their independence, prudence, and selfishness. 4.2% of respondents exhibit an "aggressive" type. They are demanding, straightforward, tough and can be hostile towards others. 6.2% have a suspicious type of attitude towards people around them, which indicates unsociability, secrecy, suspicion and touchiness of students. 12.5% of respondents have a subordinate type of relations. Such students are usually modest, compliant, emotionally reserved and do not have their own opinion. 10.4% had a dependent type of interpersonal relations, which manifests itself in self-doubt, anxiety, obedience, gullibility and dependence on other people's opinions. The friendly type is expressed in 22.9% of students. They are focused on a compromise solution to problem situations, strive to be in agreement with the opinions of others, and show warmth and friendliness in relationships. The altruistic type predominates in 4.2% of respondents. Such students are usually hyper-responsible, tactful, sympathetic and kind to people. Thus, the group we studied is characterized by friendly, selfish and authoritarian types of attitudes towards others.

The training sessions were divided into 3 blocks:

The goal of the first block is to create favorable conditions for interaction between group members and to activate group processes.

The goal of the second block is to develop interpersonal relationships and form group cohesion.

The goal of the third block is to practice new models of behavior in interpersonal interaction.

To consolidate the acquired skills of interpersonal interaction, a series of mentoring hours were held on the topics of "Interpersonal relationships as a basis for forming a socio-psychological climate in a student group", "Creating a favorable psychological climate in a group", "Let's live without conflicts", etc.

Upon completion of the formative stage of the experimental work, a control experiment was conducted aimed at identifying the dynamics of the development of interpersonal relationships of students. The diagnostic methods that were used at the ascertaining stage of the study were reused. The Wilcoxon T-criterion was used to assess the effectiveness of the implemented training program. The alternative hypothesis H1 about the difference in the results of the experimental group before and after the formative experiment was confirmed at the $p \leq 0.01$ level of significance, which indicates positive dynamics in the development of interpersonal relationships of students.

Thus, the following conclusion can be made:

1. Interpersonal relationships are one of the important factors of the emotional climate of the group and the emotional well-being of its members. Many scientists argue that the productivity of educational activities, the degree of self-realization of the student and the level of adaptation to future professional activity depend on the nature of interpersonal interactions.

2. The educational process of a medical university can be considered as an important stage in the development of effective interpersonal relationships of students.

3. The conducted empirical study confirmed the need for targeted work on the development of interpersonal relationships of students.

4. In order to develop positive interpersonal relationships of students, a psychological training "Psychology of Communication and Interpersonal Relationships" was developed and implemented.

5. The data of the control stage indicate that the developed and implemented training contributes to the development of effective interpersonal relationships, strengthening interpersonal ties, forming constructive interactions and team building.

6. For the effective development of interpersonal relationships at the stage of university education, it is necessary to create a favorable psychological climate in the group; curators to conduct educational activities to develop tolerance, cooperation, and a culture of communication; teachers of the psychological block of disciplines to develop skills for constructive solutions to many psychological problems that arise in the student environment.

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